

Mechanical characterization of novel 3D fibre-reinforced high-performance natural fibre-reinforced epoxy composites

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on the application of a novel three-dimensional (3D) orthogonal-through-the-thickness fibre reinforcement (OTT) on top of an intralaminar hybrid reinforcement architecture (2D), in order to enhance the transverse strength and fracture toughness of the composite material. A jute bidirectional plain weave fabric was the base and intralaminar hybrid (2D), as well as 3D OTT reinforcements, were applied and analysed in tensile testing. Curauá, sisal, ramie, hemp and glass fibres were the secondary fibre reinforcement phases. It was found that the novel architecture kept the in-plane mechanical properties while affording likely significantly increased transverse mechanical properties.

KEYWORDS

natural fibres, mechanical properties, 3D architecture, hybrid composites.

INTRODUCTION

Natural fibre-reinforced composites (NFRCs) have grown in popularity in recent decades due to the increasing pressure from governments all over the world for the decrease of fossil fuel dependency. Natural fibres afford many advantages such as light weight, low cost and low environmental impact. Their composites have been used in many industries over the decades such as the automotive industry, however, their applications have been relegated to non-structural (Li et al., 2020). This is due to the fact that their mechanical properties are lower than their more commonly used synthetic composite counterparts. Therefore, a vital area of study for NFRCs is the enhancement of the material properties of the composites. Of these, the hybridization technique has been demonstrated to be the most capable thus far (Cavalcanti et al., 2019). This technique is based on the concept of using more than one reinforcement fibre phases in different architectures in order to fabricate a new material with improved properties. The reinforcement architecture may be intralaminar (fibre phases in the same lamina) or interlaminar (fibre phases on different laminae). Both techniques present good results and have their pros and cons. Another area of great interest for composite materials is the fact that the material will never be isotropic. That is, different directions will present different mechanical properties. For example, for a material reinforced with symmetric bidirectional fabrics, the z (through the composite thickness) direction (transverse) properties will be starkly different from the x and y (in-plane) properties. This material would be called orthotropic. This asymmetry of properties gives rise to many issues such as delamination failures in adhesive bonding as well as lower fracture toughness and impact resistance due to a lack of reinforcement in the z direction (de Queiroz & Banea, 2022). In this context, this technique of transverse reinforcement of a fibre-reinforced composite could tackle the issues of delamination in adhesive bonding, increase the fatigue life of structures and significantly improve the performance under impact conditions. However, care must be taken regarding the z-bonder fibre fraction such that the in-plane material properties do not decrease significantly. The objective of this research is the study of a novel 3D OTT (orthogonal through-the-thickness) fibre-

reinforcement that aims at fabricating composite materials that have the benefit of increased delamination resistance and fracture toughness while maintaining their original in-plane mechanical properties.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Pure jute fibre bidirectional fabrics (P9, supplied by Sisalsul (São Paulo, Brazil)), were used as a base for the composite architecture. The intralaminar reinforcement technique was used in order to reinforce the jute fabrics. The reason for this is to essentially fabricate “unidirectional” (UD) fabrics with the secondary reinforcement fibre phases (i.e., curauá, sisal, ramie and hemp) since there are no commercially available UD fabrics of these fibres. The curauá fibres used were in-natura and supplied by the Federal University of Pará (Pará, Brazil). The curauá fibre bundles were manually selected and washed with distilled water in order to remove dirt and other impurities. They were then dried in an oven at 100 °C until completely dry. Five layers of woven fabrics were used to fabricate the composite panels for all cases. The sisal (APAEB 700/1, Bahia, Brazil), ramie, hemp (Luli Têxtil, Blumenau, Brazil) and glass fibres (SE1200, Owens Corning, USA) were supplied as commercially available fibre rovings. The intralaminar reinforcement was fabricated via weaving the fibres through the plain weave jute base fabric in a pattern that skipped no columns and interweaved the weft rows by 8 spaces (see Fig. 1a). As previously mentioned, the reason for this 2D architecture choice was to create UD hybrid fabrics as well as not significantly increase the crimpness (fabric waviness) of the fabric by spacing the entry and exit points of the secondary fibre. Next, for the 3D specimens, a 3D OTT reinforcement was woven through the 5 layers by way of a PLA 3D printed mask in order to control the architecture geometry of the dry preforms (see Fig. 1b and e). In other words, the intralaminar only reinforced fabrics were placed between the 3D printed mask and the 3D reinforcement was woven through 5 layers to create the dry 3D fibre-reinforced preforms for all cases. A detail of the differences between the 2D and 3D reinforcement architectures can be seen in Fig. 1c, where the intralaminar weaving can be clearly seen against the jute fabric as well as the points of entry of the through-the-thickness reinforcement. Furthermore, a representative cross-sectional view of the curauá composite can be seen in Fig. 1d, and the 3D reinforcement can be seen more clearly. The fibre weight fractions (in relation to the total weight of the fibre phases, resin and hardener) were approx. 30%, 24%, 20%, 22% and 18% for the curauá, sisal, ramie, hemp and glass intralaminar (2D) specimens, respectively. For the 3D fibre reinforcements, the weight fractions were approx. 3%, 2%, 4%, 1% and 2%, respectively. Pure synthetic fibre-reinforced specimens using bidirectional fabrics were also fabricated as a point of comparison of material properties (GFRP). Bidirectional fibre fabrics were used, and the same fabrication technique was applied (RE200P bidirectional glass fabrics (Barracuda Advanced Composites, SP, Brazil). A bicomponent epoxy resin matrix, HEX 135 SLOW (Barracuda Advanced Composites, SP, Brazil), was used in order to fabricate the composite panels. The fabrication process was the compression molding via a steel mould and a heated plate hydraulic press. The specimens were cut via tungsten carbide blade in the geometry based on the ASTM D 3039 international standard.

a)

b)

Figure 1: Representative GLASS composites, a) 2D, b) 3D, c) detail of the architecture, d) cross-section view of the CURAUÁ composite and e) schematic of the 3D printed PLA mask used.

All the composite materials were characterised by tensile tests using a universal Instron®5966 testing machine (Norwood, Massachusetts, USA). A 10 kN load cell and a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min was used. A clip-gauge extensometer was used to record the true strain.

A SEM analysis was performed on the fracture surface of the specimens using a high-resolution Scanning Electron Microscopy, FEI Inspect™ with a 20 KV voltage acceleration available at the Nanotechnology Characterization Laboratory of the National Institute of Technology, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. The samples were coated with a Platinum layer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 presents representative stress-strain curves of all the tested specimens as a function of fibre architecture. It can be seen from Fig. 3 that a significant variance in behaviour and rigidity occurred as a function of composite material. As expected, the neat synthetic composite presented the highest rigidity and stress at failure. A range of tensile moduli are visible from the stiffest (GFRP) to the least stiff (JFRP). The general behaviour evolution of the specimens was brittle, with a more mixed brittle/ductile behaviour observed for the natural hybrid composites.

Figure 2: Representative stress-strain curves as a function of reinforcement architecture.

The mechanical properties of the adherend materials are summarised in Table 3. It can be seen, somewhat surprisingly, that the 3D architecture reinforcement presented no significant variation when compared to the 2D specimens, with the exception of the HEMP specimens. According to the available literature (for synthetic fibre-reinforced composites), a decrease in the in-plane mechanical properties is to be expected as a trade-off for the higher fracture toughness and transverse composite properties afforded by the 3D architecture (Stig & Hallström, 2009). This is likely due to the chosen architecture, for two reasons; first, the ratio of the length of the 3D fibres in the main direction (the ones that are on the surfaces of the composite) compared to the ones in the transverse direction (going through-the-thickness), is approx. 6. That means that they are helping to resist the main direction of loading and manage to counter the deleterious effect of the orthogonal direction reinforcement. Second, the number of points in which the 3D fibre goes through the composite specimen in the useful area of the tensile coupon (the exposed specimen between the clamps of the machine) is approx. 5. This is relevant due to the fact that these points are likely high stress concentration points (high crimp of the fibre and a resin-rich zone).

All the hybrid cases presented significant enhancements when compared to the neat JFRP. For example, the HEMP specimens presented an improvement in tensile strength of approx. 15% and 28% for the 2D and 3D cases, respectively. For the RAMIE cases these improvements were approx. 25%. Similarly for the SISAL specimens, enhancements of approx. 35% were observed. The CURAUÁ specimens presented the most significant improvements in tensile strength as a function of architecture of approx. 58%. A similar improvement was observed when the GLASS and GFRP specimens are compared to the JFRP in tensile strength of approx. 61% and 68%, respectively. These results demonstrate that not only the hybridization technique presents significant improvements when compared to the non-reinforced case, the improvements depend significantly on the secondary reinforcement phase. Furthermore, as previously mentioned, the variations of tensile strength for all cases when the 2D is compared to the 3D, was not significant, with the exception of the HEMP specimens (approx. 15% variation). It is noteworthy that the CURAUÁ composites presented significantly high tensile strength, reaching approx. 93% and 77% of the GLASS and GFRP specimens, respectively.

In terms of the stiffness, a similar trend is observed where all the hybrid specimens presented enhancements when compared to the JFRP. For example, the HEMP specimens presented an improvement of approx. 25%. For the RAMIE cases these improvements were approx. 43%. Similarly

for the SISAL specimens, enhancements of approx. 40% were observed. The CURAUÁ specimens presented the most significant improvements in stiffness as a function of architecture of approx. 62% and 66% for the 2D and 3D specimens, respectively. A similar enhancement was observed when the GLASS and GFRP specimens are compared to the JFRP in stiffness of approx. 55% and 64%, respectively. Similar to the tensile strength, the CURAUÁ specimens surpassed the GLASS and GFRP ones in stiffness by approx. 32% and 5%, respectively.

The tensile strain was also affected by the fibre type and architecture. Generally, a more ductile secondary fibre phase increased the strain at failure, while a less ductile one kept it at approx. 1%, which is due to the main fibre phase (jute) already being quite brittle (de Queiroz & Banea, 2022). The general trends observed in this study, when the in-plane tensile properties of 3D composites are compared to their 2D counterparts is in accordance with the available literature for synthetic composites, where variations of plus or minus 20% are expected as a function of 3D architectures (Mouritz & Cox, 2010). Therefore, the pre-existing understanding of the mechanistic phenomena for the synthetic composites may be applied to the 3D NFRC specimens such as numerical modelling. The failure modes of the tensile specimens were generally brittle for the hybrid specimens, due to the brittle nature of the jute fibre. On the other hand, for the pure synthetic specimens a mixed mode of delamination was observed. Overall, it was found that the chosen 3D + 2D reinforcement architecture presented an optimum balance which affords the desired transverse property increase due to the presence of the OTT fibres as well as maintaining the mechanical properties of the composites.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the adherends.

Composite type	Tensile strength (MPa)	Young's modulus (GPa)	Tensile strain (%)
JFRP	63.13 ± 0.78	6.06 ± 0.46	1.15 ± 0.0015
HEMP 2D	74.54 ± 3.12	8.04 ± 1.01	1.28 ± 0.001
HEMP 3D	87.78 ± 9.17	8.16 ± 0.99	1.46 ± 0.0032
RAMIE 2D	85.25 ± 4.27	10.69 ± 1.44	1.15 ± 0.0019
RAMIE 3D	84.77 ± 8.96	10.74 ± 1.66	1.26 ± 0.0032
SISAL 2D	96.98 ± 7.57	10.16 ± 0.12	1.04 ± 0.002
SISAL 3D	91.88 ± 7.04	9.90 ± 1.19	1.76 ± 0.006
CURAUÁ 2D	150.26 ± 12.72	17.79 ± 2.81	1.04 ± 0.002
CURAUÁ 3D	145.01 ± 10.81	15.78 ± 0.72	1.08 ± 0.001
GLASS 2D	161.26 ± 8.72	13.45 ± 1.66	1.59 ± 0.002
GLASS 3D	162.26 ± 9.72	13.83 ± 0.75	1.45 ± 0.0008
GFRP	197.85 ± 19.54	20.16 ± 4.86	2.00

Representative SEM images can be seen in Fig. 3 for the SISAL, CURAUÁ and GLASS specimens. It can be seen from Fig. 3 that significant morphological differences exist as a function of the reinforcement fibre. For example, the surface of the curauá fibre (see Fig. 3a) presents well defined ridges with an almost star-like cross section. This improves the mechanical interlocking with the resin matrix. From Fig. 3b, a more inhomogeneous bundle of thin fibres can be observed for the SISAL ones. While, for the GLASS specimens, a good fibre resin interface can be observed and a ductile fracture of the glass fibres can be seen. These morphological observations support the mechanical findings.

Figure 3: Representative SEM images of a) CURAUÁ, b) SISAL and c) GLASS tensile failure specimens.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a novel 3D OTT (orthogonal through-the-thickness) reinforcement architecture was analysed in tandem with an intralaminar reinforcement architecture with a variety of different secondary fibre phases (i.e., jute bidirectional fabric main phase, secondary phases as intralaminar and 3D reinforcement). It was observed that, with the exception of the HEMP specimens, no significant variation was observed in the in-plane tensile properties of the composites. This has been found to be in accordance with the prevailing literature of synthetic 3D composites. Furthermore, the CURAUÁ composites presented significantly high tensile strength and stiffness, reaching approx. 93% and 77% of the GLASS and GFRP composite strength and surpassing them in stiffness by approx. 32% and 5%, respectively. These results demonstrate the possibility of application of 3D reinforcements in NFRCs in uses where the transverse properties are vital, without any significant compromise in in-plane tensile properties as well as demonstrating the viability of CURAUÁ as a powerful option as reinforcement.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.